

UDC: 616.8-009

EPILEPSY IN CHILDREN IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN: CHALLENGES OF DIAGNOSIS, THERAPY, AND SOCIAL STIGMA

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Abstract. *Childhood epilepsy is one of the most common chronic neurological disorders, affecting approximately 0.5–1% of the pediatric population. The aim of this review article was to analyze the current challenges associated with childhood epilepsy in the Republic of Kazakhstan, including issues of diagnosis, therapy, social stigma, and public health policy.*

Methods: *We conducted a review of recent publications in international and Kazakhstani medical journals, reports by the World Health Organization (WHO), national statistical data from the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as well as regulatory documents related to epilepsy treatment and pharmaceutical provision.*

Results: *The study revealed that epilepsy remains a significant medical and social issue in the Republic of Kazakhstan, requiring a comprehensive approach at the levels of healthcare, education, and society as a whole. There is insufficient training among primary care providers, leading to both under- and overdiagnosis of epilepsy, especially in children and adolescents. A shortage of pediatric epileptologists and specialized diagnostic centers is evident. Although the state provides antiepileptic drugs (AEDs), the list of available medications is limited and does not always meet the needs of patients with pharmacoresistant forms. Many patients tend to hide their diagnosis, which negatively affects prognosis and reduces treatment adherence.*

Keywords: *epilepsy, children, diagnosis, treatment, antiepileptic drugs.*

**ҚАЗАҚСТАН РЕСПУБЛИКАСЫНДАҒЫ БАЛАЛАР ЭПИЛЕПСИЯСЫ:
ДИАГНОСТИКА, ЕМДЕУ ЖӘНЕ ӘЛЕУМЕТТІК СТИГМА МӘСЕЛЕЛЕРІ**

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Түйіндеме. Балалар эпилепсиясы — балалардың шамамен 0,5–1% қамтитын ең кең таралған созылмалы неврологиялық аурулардың бірі. Осы шолулық мақаланың мақсаты — Қазақстан Республикасындағы балалар эпилепсиясына қатысты өзекті мәселелерді, соның ішінде диагностикалау, емдеу, әлеуметтік стигма және мемлекеттік саясатқа байланысты сұрақтарды талдау болды.

Әдістер: Біз халықаралық және қазақстандық медициналық журналдарда жарияланған заманауи материалдарды, Дүниежүзілік денсаулық сақтау ұйымының (ДДҰ) есептерін, ҚР Денсаулық сақтау министрлігінің ұлттық статистикалық деректерін және эпилепсияны емдеуге және дәрілік қамтамасыз етуге қатысты нормативтік құжаттарды сараладық.

Нәтижелер: Зерттеу нәтижесінде эпилепсия Қазақстан Республикасында денсаулық сақтау, білім беру және қоғам деңгейінде кешенді көзқарасты қажет ететін маңызды медициналық және әлеуметтік мәселе болып қалуда деген қорытынды жасалды. Елде бастапқы буын дәрігерлерінің жеткіліксіз дайындығы салдарынан, әсіресе балалар мен жасөспірімдер арасында эпилепсияның гипо- және гипердиагностикасы жиі кездеседі. Балалар эпилептологтары мен арнайы диагностикалық орталықтардың тапшылығы байқалады. Мемлекет тарапынан антиэпилептикалық препараттар (АЭП) тегін беріледі, алайда олардың тізімі шектеулі және фармакорезистентті түрлермен ауыратын науқастардың қажеттіліктеріне әрдайым сай келе бермейді. Көптеген науқастар диагноздарын жасырады, бұл аурудың болжамын нашарлатып, емге бейімділікті төмендетеді.

Түйінді сөздер: эпилепсия, балалар, диагностика, емдеу, антиэпилептикалық препараттар.

ЭПИЛЕПСИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ КАЗАХСТАН: ПРОБЛЕМЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ, ТЕРАПИИ И СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ СТИГМЫ

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Резюме. Эпилепсия у детей — одно из наиболее распространённых хронических неврологических заболеваний, которое затрагивает около 0,5–1% детского населения.

Целью данной обзорной статьи было проанализировать актуальные проблемы, связанные с эпилепсией у детей в Республике Казахстан, включая вопросы диагностики, терапии, социальной стигмы и государственной политики.

Методы: Нами был проведён обзор актуальных публикаций в международных и казахстанских медицинских журналах, отчётов Всемирной организации здравоохранения (ВОЗ), национальных статистических данных Министерства здравоохранения РК, а также нормативных документов, касающихся лечения эпилепсии и фармакологического обеспечения.

Результаты: В результате исследования был сделан вывод, что эпилепсия в Республике Казахстан остаётся значимой медицинской и социальной проблемой, требующей комплексного подхода на уровне здравоохранения, образования и общества в целом. В Казахстане имеется недостаточная подготовка специалистов первичного звена, которая приводит к гипо- и гипердиагностике эпилепсии, особенно у детей и подростков. Наблюдается дефицит детских эпилептологов и профильных центров диагностики. Государственное обеспечение противоэпилептическими препаратами (ПЭП) осуществляется, однако список препаратов ограничен и не всегда соответствует потребностям пациентов с фармакорезистентными формами. Пациенты часто скрывают диагноз, что ухудшает прогноз и снижает приверженность к лечению.

Ключевые слова: эпилепсия, дети, диагностика, лечение, антиэпилептические препараты.

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), epilepsy accounts for approximately 1% of the global burden of disease and ranks fourth among neuropsychiatric disorders—following depression, alcoholism, and cerebrovascular diseases. In terms of its impact on public health, epilepsy is comparable to major malignancies such as breast and lung cancer [1]. Worldwide, more than 70 million people suffer from epilepsy [2,3]. The condition is characterized by a chronic predisposition to spontaneous epileptic seizures and is associated with a wide range of neurobiological, cognitive, and psychosocial impairments [3,4].

Epilepsy is one of the most common neurological disorders, affecting people of all ages, races, social classes, and geographical regions. It is a brain disorder characterized by a persistent predisposition to seizures, along with the neurobiological, cognitive, psychological, and social consequences of recurrent seizures [5].

Methods

A literature search was conducted in scientific databases such as PubMed, Web of Science, Cochrane, and Wiley using the keywords: “epilepsy,” “children,” “diagnosis,” “treatment,” and “antiepileptic drugs.” A total of 52 articles published between 2005 and 2025 were analyzed.

In accordance with current understanding of the pathogenesis of epilepsy, seizure types, and their causes, the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) has updated its classification. The latest revision of the classification of seizures and epilepsies (2017–2022) offers a more accurate and clinically meaningful system focused on diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment [6]. As a result of years of dedicated work by experts, in 2022 the ILAE published a set of documents outlining the updated definitions and classification of epileptic syndromes. The ILAE defined an epileptic syndrome as: “A characteristic cluster of clinical and electroencephalographic features, often associated with specific etiological factors (structural, genetic, metabolic, immune, or infectious).”

Discussion

There are very few doctors in Kazakhstan specializing in research on childhood epilepsy. As a result, there is a limited number of publications on epilepsy in both national and international medical journals. This is partly due to the lack of accurate statistical data on epilepsy patients in Kazakhstan, as many individuals do not seek medical assistance out of fear of societal discrimination. Because of stigma and discrimination associated with epilepsy in the country, many people avoid registering at clinics and, consequently, do not receive appropriate treatment.

One of the studies conducted in Kazakhstan focused on assessing the epidemiology of epilepsy using a large-scale administrative healthcare database covering the years 2014–2020. Utilizing the Unified National Electronic Health System of Kazakhstan over a seven-year period, researchers analyzed incidence and prevalence rates, disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), and all-cause mortality related to epilepsy [7].

The study identified a number of sociodemographic, mental, behavioral, and neurological factors influencing the survival of epilepsy patients. The initial cohort included 82,907 individuals.

During the study period, there was a significant increase in the incidence of epilepsy—from 26.15 to 88.80 cases per 100,000 population. A similar trend was observed in prevalence rates, which tripled from 26.06 in 2014 to 73.10 in 2020. Despite fluctuations in mortality across different years, the highest mortality rates were recorded among elderly patients (9.97) and children (2.98 per 1,000 person-years). DALY calculations (disability-adjusted life years) demonstrated a high overall burden of the disease: a total of 153,532 DALYs were recorded, corresponding to 824.5 per 100,000 population. It is worth noting that a portion of the sample was lost at various stages of observation. The presence of comorbid conditions such as cerebral palsy (adjusted hazard ratio — aHR 2.23) and central nervous system atrophy (aHR 27.79) significantly increased the risk of all-cause mortality. There was also a noted trend toward higher mortality among patients with extrapyramidal and movement disorders (aHR 2.16, $p = 0.06$) and demyelinating diseases of the central nervous system (aHR 6.36, $p = 0.06$).

One of the major problems in Kazakhstan is the lack of epilepsy centers in major cities. Currently, the only epilepsy center in the country is located in Astana, within the Hospital of the Medical Center of the Presidential Affairs Administration, which has been operating since 2018. Epileptologists at this center specialize in presurgical evaluation of epilepsy in both adults and children.

There is a severe shortage of specialists in Kazakhstan. Many physicians are unwilling to work in the field of epileptology, considering it too complex and showing little interest in working with epilepsy patients. Furthermore, there is a limited number of qualified neurologist-epileptologists who teach epileptology in medical universities. An epileptologist is expected to have a broad set of skills, including proficiency in EEG acquisition and interpretation, MRI analysis, knowledge of epilepsy protocols, the ability to properly prescribe antiepileptic drugs, and the expertise to timely recognize and diagnose various types of epilepsy.

A second significant issue is the occurrence of seizures in patients that clinically resemble epilepsy but originate from other causes. This poses a global diagnostic challenge: even in leading epilepsy centers worldwide, the rate of misdiagnosis can reach 40–70%. Such seizure-like episodes may be caused by various conditions, including cardiac arrhythmias, vascular pathologies, and endocrine disorders (including dysfunctions of the adrenal glands, gonads, pituitary gland, and thyroid). In addition, seizure-like reactions in young individuals can sometimes be triggered by excessive consumption of energy drinks.

The third significant issue is the limited access to antiepileptic drugs (AEDs). Although approximately 35 different AEDs are used in clinical practice worldwide, only 11 are officially registered in Kazakhstan. While this selection is generally sufficient for the basic treatment of the most common forms of epilepsy, the lack of specific medications for rare or treatment-resistant forms can lead to deterioration in patients' conditions.

At the same time, it is important to note that all anticonvulsant medications in Kazakhstan are provided to patients free of charge. The state does supply antiepileptic drugs; however, the list is limited and does not always meet the needs of patients with pharmacoresistant epilepsy. Modern and individualized treatment regimens are not widely implemented, especially in regional areas. Surgical treatment is available only in a few specialized medical institutions.

At present, one of the major problems in Kazakhstan remains the late diagnosis of epilepsy, particularly in rural regions. This is due to insufficient public awareness, limited access to qualified neurological care, and a shortage of modern diagnostic tools such as video-EEG monitoring and high-resolution magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [8].

In addition, overdiagnosis and misinterpretation of clinical manifestations are frequently observed, especially in children. This can lead to the unnecessary prescription of antiepileptic drugs or, conversely, to an underestimation of the severity of the condition [9].

Social stigma often causes many patients to hide their diagnosis, avoid seeking medical help, or discontinue medication out of fear of public disclosure. This significantly worsens the prognosis

and reduces quality of life [10]. There is also a lack of data on genetic epilepsy in Kazakhstan, despite its unique clinical course and management implications [11].

Issues related to the individualization of therapy also remain unresolved. Physicians often have to prescribe treatment “blindly” due to the unavailability of genetic and metabolic testing, which could help in selecting the most effective therapy for pharmacoresistant forms of epilepsy.

Conclusion

Thus, addressing the existing challenges requires comprehensive measures: improving the qualifications of primary care physicians and neurologists; developing specialized centers for the diagnosis and treatment of epilepsy; expanding the list of free antiepileptic drugs to include new-generation medications; conducting public awareness and educational campaigns; and implementing programs for social adaptation and patient support. Only through such integrated efforts can the quality of life of epilepsy patients be improved and the social impact of epilepsy in the Republic of Kazakhstan be reduced.

Conflict of Interest. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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